

First sustainability report: Environmental, economic and social Deliverable 8.2

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Lead Partner: ITENE

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The SCALIBUR project aims to demonstrate new valorization routes, such as biobased products, for urban biowaste. Therefore, SCALIBUR enables the formation of a partnership which includes waste management companies, technology developers, researchers and end users; to recover and transform biowaste from three municipalities, Madrid (ES), Albano (IT), and Kozani (EL), into value added products. These new value chains will transform HORECA waste into proteins, lipids and chitin from insect rearing, while the organic fraction of MSW will be hydrolyzed into sugars that will be further converted into biopesticides and bioplastics by fermentation. Moreover, the resulting biogas from MSW and USS will be upgraded by bioelectrochemical treatment to produce commodity chemicals and bioplastics.

This WP is focused on assessing environmental, techno-economic, social impacts and safety aspects of the SCALIBUR processes. This evaluation will include techno-economical, environmental and social levels. Environmental impacts are going to be analyzed through the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) as well as the Social level. The technological developments will be analyzed under an engineering-oriented approach for the techno-economic assessment of the developed processes.

This deliverable 8.2 "First sustainability report: Environmental, Economic and social" provides the first results of the LCA and the social assessment, as well as the actions that have been carried out for the techno-economic assessment. Regarding the LCA assessment, the first results in relation to the current situation of the different municipalities have been calculated and will serve to compare with the improvements made by SCALIBUR in the value chains. In relation to the social assessment, the first questionnaires that will be used are presented in this deliverable, as well as the methodology that will be followed. Finally, for the techno-economic assessment, the first steps have been followed, and a template for collecting the information have been developed and it is detailed in this deliverable.

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